

**CERTAIN ASPECTS OF CLASSIFICATION OF CRIMES BY ERROR
IN CRIMINAL LAW**

Masharifov Sirojbek Bahadirovich

Tashkent State Law University

independent researcher

Dean of Khorezm Region Legal Technical College

masharifovs585gmail.com

Abstract: In this article, the commission of a crime by a person by mistake and its criminal legal aspects were analyzed. In addition, the article contains some suggestions regarding legal and factual error and its expression in some articles of the criminal code and its reflection in the code.

Key words: subjective side of crime, factual error, legal error, qualification of crimes.

**НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ ПРЕСТУПЛЕНИЙ
ПО ОШИБКЕ В УГОЛОВНОМ ПРАВЕ**

Сирожбек Баходирович Машарифов

независимый исследователь

Ташкентский государственный юридический университет

Ташкент, Узбекистан

masharifovs585gmail.com

Аннотация: В данной статье были проанализированы совершение преступления лицом по ошибке и его уголовно-правовые аспекты. Кроме того, в статье содержатся некоторые предложения относительно юридической и

фактологической ошибки и ее проявления в отдельных статьях УК РФ и ее отражения в кодексе.

Ключевые слова: субъективная сторона преступления, фактическая ошибка, юридическая ошибка, квалификация преступлений.

A person's mistake in committing a crime affects the content, form, level and extent of the crime. For this reason, it determines the limits of subjective guilt in the consideration of each criminal case, defines the qualification of the act, the application of many institutions of criminal law, the limits of criminal liability and punishment. In this case, a person makes a mistake regarding his legal or factual (objective) situation regarding the act he wants to commit. This does not rule out his criminality. But this mistake has a certain influence on the evaluation of the act, and for this reason, the concept of mistake in criminal law is studied theoretically and practically. The question of error and its effect on guilt and criminal liability is dealt with by criminal law theory and case law. Criminal law does not stop at the mistake in the process of committing a crime, but this does not reduce its criminal legal importance. But this situation also leads to the emergence of different opinions about the error. The problems related to the legal assessment of a person's deception in committing a socially significant act are not new to the science of criminal law. Some of its aspects, as a rule, in the study of the subjective side of crime B.S. Volkov, P.S. Dagel, G.A. Zlobin, V.E.V. Luneeva, A.V. Naumova, B.S. Nikiforova, K Considered in the works of Russian legal scholars such as F. Tikhonova. In recent years, interest in the problem of errors in criminal law has increased. In the theory of criminal law, there are different interpretations of the concept of error that are similar to each other. Some scholars understand error as a person's delusion about the real and legal features of the act[1], others interpret it as a person's misunderstanding of the real and legal features or characteristics of the committed act and its consequences[2], others interpret it as a person's wrong assessment of his behavior defined as[3]. From the above explanations, we can see different features of the concept of error. In particular, he interpreted it as a state of not knowing the legal value of a person's act or a person making a mistake in relation to

the legal status of the act he committed. From the comments of Russian scientists, we can come to the following conclusion. Mistakes in the steps of committing a crime are mistakes in relation to the criminal purpose, mistakes in the planning stage of the crime, in which a person may make a mistake in relation to the object of the crime or the victim, or the criminality of the act. The most important thing is that the error at the time of committing the crime is the realization of the criminal purpose, and its qualitative and quantitative indicators are different. At the next stage, there is a mistake regarding the origin of the criminal consequence and its nature.

We will also consider the opinions of local legal scholars about the concept of mistake. For example, in Rustamboyev's opinion, "Mistake is a mistake or a wrong perception, a wrong assessment by a person in relation to the objective characteristics of his socially dangerous act as a crime [4]". In this explanation, we can understand that the concept of error is a mental symbol. Many legal sources explain that a mistake in criminal law is an incorrect assessment by a person who has violated the law of the actual or legal nature of his actions or inaction and their consequences. This isox, in our opinion, reveals the situation more fully. The mistake is not only related to the imagination of the person who committed the act, but also related to his level. In some sources, the error refers to the criminal consequences that can result from professional or activity-related errors, which also explains that the concept of error is a broad concept. In some cases, this can greatly affect the sentence of a person accused of a particular crime, so it is important to be clear about what the mistakes are and to think deeply before committing them. By analyzing the deep explanation of the mistake, we will be able to determine the social danger of the criminal. When a crime is committed, certain circumstances important for his legal evaluation may be wrongly reflected in the mind of a person. This is not surprising, because people usually make mistakes. However, the deception of a person who has committed a particular crime is of particular interest, because it is directly related to his guilt, ultimately, to the assessment of his deed. The presence of a mistake can significantly affect the qualification of the

committed act, because it is covered by the signs of the subjective side of the crime, which determine the nature and content of intellectual and volitional processes.

A person's mistake in relation to the legal assessment of a socially dangerous act committed by him is a consequence of the commission of a crime by the criminal law the various legal consequences that may arise and to them implies a differentiated system of relative responsibility. Based on this, one or another form of responsibility or another wrong about the signs that are the basis for the application of legal consequences Various errors can occur in relation to having an imagination. For example, the criminal law for a theft committed by a person is a conditional sentence making the mistake of imagining what it means to use possible, but the criminal law prohibits imprisonment for theft or other types of punishment. Also guilty The cases of committing a crime, imagining that he will be released from responsibility due to sincere remorse, reconciliation with the victim, are no exception to this.

A factual error is a wrong perception of the circumstances of the objective signs that determine the specifics of the crime and the level of social danger. That is, misunderstanding and incorrect assessment of the subject of the crime; wrongly imagining the object of the crime, wrongly imagining the characteristics of action or inaction is wrongly imagining the severity of the resulting consequences, the circumstances that aggravate the development of the causal relationship [5]. Most of the time, a reasonable person correctly assesses the objectively formed situation around him in his mind and where he acts. But sometimes a person has a wrong idea about what happens after what he does. In simple words, a person makes a mistake and he misrepresents all the circumstances of the offense and misjudges the specifics of what was committed and the conditions of the crime. We can see a more accurate explanation of the concept of factual error in B. Matmuratov as follows. In his opinion, in the case of factual error, the objective signs of the act committed by a person are his mistake about the dangerousness of it. These mistakes can be based on the object and subject of the crime, the identity of the victim, the nature of the crime, the method of committing the crime and the weapons used, causality, level of responsibility and other

features [6]. In this case, while walking in a taxi, the person took the taxi driver's bag, thinking it had money in it, and when he opened it, he saw that it contained drugs. In this case, his action should be qualified according to Article 169 of the Criminal Code, if he knew that there was a narcotic substance in the bag, according to Article 25-169 and Article 271. The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not provide for legal grounds for factual error. This is mainly the research object of criminal law theory. To mistake the object of crime is to misrepresent the social and legal nature of the object being attacked. In legal literature, the error is divided into two types. First, the person thinks that he is attacking a certain object, when in fact the aggression is directed at a different object than the subject thinks. For example, a subject thinks that he is stealing a drug from a pharmacy, when in fact the stolen drug is a drug intended for the treatment of a specific disease. When such a mistake is made, it is qualified according to the direction of the intention. In the above example, the person is charged with assault for stealing a drug, not a drug. But it should not be overlooked that it is impossible not to reckon with an object that is not covered by the intention of the subject. In this case, the perpetrator is held accountable not for the object of the crime, which is not covered by the subjective consciousness of the person, but for the purposeful attack on the object, for the attempt to commit that crime [7]. In this situation, it is appropriate to qualify the act based on the specifics of the object to which the criminal purpose of the intention is directed. Most of the time, a sane person in his subconscious correctly assesses the objectively formed situation that surrounds him and where he is acting. But sometimes a person has a wrong idea about the circumstances of his actions. In simple words, a person makes a mistake and he misrepresents all the circumstances of the crime and incorrectly evaluates the specific features of the committed act and the conditions of the commission of the crime. As the dangerousness of the crime is determined by many circumstances, in turn, the factual error of the person can also be different in terms of social danger and level of commission and consequences. The criminal-legal content of the factual error, its impact on the element of the crime and the nature and consequences of the social

danger is determined by the fact that the person is wrong, imagines or evaluates the error.

Factual errors can be divided into the following types, based on perceptions arising from misunderstanding and evaluation of the subject matter:

- regarding the social danger of the committed act;
- in relation to the object of aggression;
- in relation to the delivered consequence;
- in relation to the causal connection;

- aggravating circumstances [8]. This division is certainly not complete. We will briefly explain the above types of factual error by Rustamboev. In a mistake regarding the social danger of the committed act, a person commits a mistake in practice regarding the object of his act as a crime. That is, the fact that the object stolen by a person, thinking that it has a certain value, does not have value means that his act is not completed, and his act leads to qualification as an attempt to commit this crime. Or some crimes require it to be committed only intentionally, and we cannot consider it a crime for a person named A to pass counterfeit money thinking it is real. It is seen in the fact that the person who committed the wrong act against the object of aggression has a wrong idea about the object of the crime. This mistake is actually related to the form of the intention, that is, the intention is aimed at the person chosen by the criminal, but he makes a mistake in identifying the object or criminally assaulting him. In this case, we will be able to explain the types of mistakes in relation to the subject of the crime and the victim. Their generality is determined by the person's mistake in relation to the sign of the crime object. In this process, the issue of the subject of the crime and the suitability of the victim will certainly arise. In this case, the guilt depends on the criminal intent and it is qualified as intent. For example, A may think that B is lewd and lascivious to a 16-year-old minor, but B turns out to be a 17-year-old minor. In this case, the significance of qualifying this act as an assassination is related to the fact that the target of the original attack is protected by the criminal law. We will analyze the concept of error in relation to the consequences. In this, a person first realizes the

estimated harm he can cause before committing a crime. But due to various reasons, the damage caused by the execution of the act may be less or exceed the criminal plan. We can cite different forms of this error. Among them, we can give such forms as quality, volume, and quantity indicators. A mistake in relation to the quality of the consequence is expressed in the fact that a social risk that is caused by a person's actions does not actually occur, or that a different or more factual consequence occurs than what he or she could have foreseen. Mistake of the offender regarding the amount of his socially dangerous act is seen in his mistaken perception of the severity of the crime. In this case, the amount of damage is more significant than in specific crimes and may affect eligibility. This occurs mainly in crimes in the field of economy. In this case, the person's act is qualified as having caused more serious damage. The fallacy of causation is the mistaken assumption that there is a causal connection between the act itself and the resulting outcome. In this case, a person can understand only the causal connection that he can understand, and in fact, the development of the event may not depend on him.

Based on the above considerations, we would like to make the following suggestions:

1. In our opinion, by categorizing the concept of error as subjective and objective error, we believe that subjective error should not affect the qualification, and objective error should affect the qualification of the act. The reason for this is that the act of the subject is not judged by his imagination, it is judged by the criminal law.

2. By enriching the forms of subjective, i.e., legal error, it is necessary to study his willful and mental states, taking into account the fact that in criminal law it becomes possible to study the personality of the criminal in more depth.

3. Factual error (objective or real) must be taken into account when qualifying the act. However, it is necessary to qualify the act without forgetting one issue, that is, the criminal purpose is the criminal intent that arises as a result of it. The more socially dangerous the criminal intent is, the trajectory of its qualification should also cover this

level. This is certainly important in the types of crimes that require the act to be committed as a result of intent or carelessness.

4. Since crimes committed as a result of a factual error in the criminal legislation mainly require the form of guilt, we believe that it is necessary to expand the range of actions that are considered crimes only if they are committed intentionally.

5. In the theory of criminal law, we think that there is a need for a wide study of the concept of excusable mistake and culpable mistake, this concept is actually briefly described in the criminal law, in the case of the necessary defense and the last necessity, but in our opinion, this situation should be sufficiently researched.

6. As a most important consideration, in our opinion, however dangerous the intention may be, we think that by evaluating the act against the consequences, the punishment assigned to it should be proportionate to it. In this case, the person realizes that his act is socially dangerous, this is reflected in the qualification, but we think that it is appropriate to impose a punishment on the basis of the principle of justice, based on the consequences or the nature of the damage caused to him. This is the reason why in the case of a legal error, when qualifying an act committed by a person's mistaken opinion, we proceed from the requirement of the law, not from his subjective opinion, why now in a factual error, punishment should not be imposed based on the real damage caused to the object protected by the criminal law. The fact that this aspect is taken into account in our legislation indicates that the criminal law is just and humane.

REFERENCES USED:

1. Коптякова Л.И. Понятие ошибок в советском уголовном праве И их классификация. - В кн.: Проблем права, социалистической государственности И социального управления. – Свердловск: Изд-во Урал.ун-та, 1978, п.106.
2. Утевский Б.С. Курс советского уголовного права. Изд-во Ленингр. Ун-та, 1968, п.449.
3. Рарог А.И. Уголовное право Российской Федератсии. Общая часть. М.: Изд-во Юрист, 1996, п.195.

4. М.Ҳ. Рустамбайев. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жиноят ҳуқуқий курси. 1-Том. Ташкент, 2018, п. 221.
5. М.Усмоналиев. Жиноят ҳуқуқи (Умумий қисм). Дарслик. “Янги авлод” нашриёти. Ташкент, 2005, п. 222
6. Б.Матмуратов. Жиноят таркиби бўйича квалификатсия қилиш масалалари. Лессон пресс. Ташкент, 2019, п. 87.
7. М.Усмоналиев, П.Бакунов Жиноят ҳуқуқи (Умумий қисм). Дарслик. “Насаф” нашриёти. Ташкент, 2010, п. 225
8. М.Ҳ. Рустамбайев. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жиноят ҳуқуқий курси. 1-Том. Ташкент, 2018, п. 221.